

THE FABRICATION OF TWO-DIMENSIONAL CARBON FIBER REINFORCED ALUMINA COMPOSITES BY PRESSURE INFILTRATION

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SUMMARY: Using pressure infiltration can fabricate two-dimensional (2-D) textile ceramic matrix composites with uniform and dense microstructure. Based upon this processing technique, composites composed of silica sol, alumina particles, and 2-D satin weave carbon fibers were fabricated. The related processing parameters studied in this work include fiber surface treatment and fiber volume fraction. The woven carbon fabrics were treated by a liquid oxidation reaction method in order to study their surface conditions on mechanical properties of 2-D composites. Fiber volume fractions are varied by changing weave density of 2-D carbon woven fabrics. Material characterizations have been conducted by a three-point bending test and an indentation fracture toughness test. Therefore, the aim of this work is to optimize processing parameters for obtaining better mechanical properties of composites.

KEYWORDS: pressure infiltration, 2-D fabrics, liquid oxidation reaction

INTRODUCTION

In practical applications, a structure component might be subjected to multidirectional loads, resulting in the need to arrange the reinforcing fibers in more than one direction. Textile composites using tailored preforms, such as woven, knitted, or braided fabrics, are versatile to accommodate a variety of requirements, such as stability (strength/stiffness) or extensibility in desired directions and relative ease of handling in fabrication [1]. The advantages have led to the current interest in fabricating ceramic matrix composites based on textile preforms. However, the microstructure of textile ceramic matrix composites (CMCs) is significantly influenced by the processing route. For example, textile CMCs fabricated by the chemical vapor infiltration (CVI) technique normally contain high porosity which results in the stiffness reduction of the composite [2].

Several processing routes for CMCs have their respective advantages. SiC matrix ceramic composites fabricated by CVI [3] have improved mechanical properties. The advantage of CVI is that chemical vapors can react and produce pure ceramic matrix at low temperature around 1200°C. 2-D Nicalon/BN/SiC composites processed by the isothermal chemical vapor infiltration (ICVI) method [4] have better load transfer efficiency under aggressive environment than typical SiC/C/SiC composites. 2-D woven fabric SiC/SiC composites with multilayered interphases fabricated by CVI method [5,6] have both high strength and toughness due to strong interphases and large amounts of matrix cracks at saturation,

respectively. 2-D woven fabric SiC/SiC composites can be produced by a slurry infiltration method [7] associated with multiple impregnation at a lower temperature. 3-D C/SiC and C/Si₃N₄ composites made by polymer pyrolysis and repeated infiltration [8] gain their unique properties. A common advantage of these fabrication routes is that the processing temperature can be lowered to 1200°C. However, a common disadvantage of these fabrication routes is long processing time. Based on economical point of view, to cut down the processing time should be one of the important issues for fabrication of CMCs in the near future. To achieve the above goal, Liu and Parvizi-Majidi [9] tried to fabricate 3-D ceramic matrix composites with satisfactory density and uniformity in a single infiltration using the addition of solid particles to the sol during sol-gel processing of ceramic matrix composites.

Therefore, the purpose of this work is to introduce a pressure infiltration method which could fabricate 2-D woven carbon fabric reinforced alumina composites with dense microstructure. The woven carbon fabrics were treated by a liquid oxidation reaction method in order to evaluate the influence of their surface conditions on mechanical properties of 2-D woven fabric CMCs. To optimize processing parameters for obtaining better mechanical properties is the goal in this study.

MATERIAL PROCESSING

Sol and Woven Fabric Preparation

The silica sol was prepared using a modified recipe of Klein's work [10]. In this recipe, tetraethyl-orthosilicate (TEOS), ethanol, deionized water and 7 wt% of HNO₃ were mixed and stirred at a volume ratio of 1: 1: 1.6 : 0.06. All the reaction of the mixture was all at room temperature. 25 grams of the alumina powders (α - Al₂O₃, Bayer process, average particle diameter of 0.45 μ m, purity of particle of 99.9%, and a density of 2.7g/cm³) were added to the sol to prepare the infiltrate. The infiltrate was further mixed both in ultrasonic bath and electromagnetic blender in turns until the powders in the infiltrate were dispersed uniformly and well wetted.

2-D plain carbon fabrics were used as preforms. The carbon fiber is Toho T-300 fiber with tensile strength of 3200 MPa. The first kind of fabric has fiber volume fraction (V_f) of 33.7%. Each fiber yarn has 3000 fibers. Fiber has density of 1.78 g/cm³ and diameter of 8 μ m. Weave density is warp 5 yarns/cm and weft 5 yarns/cm. Fabric weight is 194 g/m². The second kind of fabric has fiber volume fraction of 21.5%. Weave density is warp 2 yarns/cm and weft 2 yarns/cm. Fabric weight is 87 g/m². Each fabric was cut as a circle of 50 mm diameter. 12 layers of the woven fabrics were stacked together and stitched by a string as a preform with a thickness 3.67 mm (first kind) and 2.78 mm (second kind), respectively. The preform was further processed by pressure infiltration to obtain composites. The woven fabrics were either untreated (as-received) or treated by liquid oxidation reaction in order to compare the effect of fiber surface conditions on mechanical properties of the composites. The treated procedure is as follows. Carbon fabrics were dipped in 35wt% nitric acid solution at 70°C for 6 hours. Then the fabrics were washed by deionized water and dried at 150°C.

Pressure Infiltration

The pressure infiltration apparatus was shown in Fig. 1, with an inner diameter of 50 mm in the cylinder, and a base cavity for collecting the liquid. The filter assembly consists of nitrate cellulose membrane filter paper with selected pore size, a wire cloth-stainless steel, and a perforated solid steel disk. The filter assembly was placed on the top of the base cavity. The wire cloth-stainless steel was used to keep the filter paper from rupture. Cylinder, filter assembly, and base were tightly sealed by thread and O-ring. Carbon fabrics were first put in the cylinder and attached to the filter assembly closely. A volume of 175 ml of infiltrate was then poured into the cylinder to infiltrate fabrics. An MTS testing machine set at constant crosshead speed mode was used to provide the infiltration pressure on the plunger. The use of a constant crosshead speed insured a gradual increase in pressure which consolidates powders inside the fabrics uniformly, and prevented filter paper from rupture. The maximum values of pressure were recorded: 46.7 MPa for the composite with untreated carbon fibers and 21.0 MPa for the composite with treated carbon fibers.

Fig. 1: Schematic diagram of pressure infiltration apparatus.

After first infiltration, the specimen was ejected and dried in an oven at 60°C for 24 hours. After the drying process, the composite was soaked in silica sol until saturation, and finally the composite green density was calculated from its dimensions and weight. Green composites were then hot pressed in a furnace (FCPHP-R-5, FRET-20, HIGH MULTI 5000, Multi-purpose High Temperature Furnace, Japan) under temperature 1600°C and pressure 25 MPa for one and half hours by first evacuated to 10^{-5} torr, and then flowing nitrogen gas. After hot pressing, the percentage theoretical densities of composites were measured. In addition, microstructure and mechanical properties of composites were also evaluated.

MATERIAL CHARACTERIZATION

The hot pressed composites were cut as specimen to evaluate mechanical properties and examine microstructure. Specimen cross sections were directly examined by a scanning electron microscope for bonding between fibers and matrix. Specimen before and after mechanical testing were embedded in urea, then polished with diamond paste and examined by an optical microscope. Specimen after mechanical testing were photographed by camera to observe their macroscopic failure.

The indentation fracture technique was adopted to determine the fracture toughness of composite materials. The Vickers diamond pyramid indenter was used to produce the crack patterns onto the well polished cross sections of specimen, which are on matrices between fiber layers. The indentation load is 5 kgw, which provides consistent indentation patterns with radial crack lengths substantially larger than the indentation diagonals. Thus, fracture toughness (K_{IC}) can be calculated by measuring the lengths of diagonals and radial cracks by using the following equation

$$K_{IC} = \beta (E/H)^{1/2} (P/c^{3/2}) \quad (1)$$

where β is a constant around 0.016, E is modulus of composites, H is hardness of composites, P is indentation load, and c is half of the crack length.

A three point bending test was adopted to measure flexural strength and modulus of composites. An MTS testing machine was used to conduct the test. The span L, width w, and height h of the specimen were designed to be 40 mm, 9 mm, and 5 mm, respectively; detailed dimensions were measured for each specimen for further calculation of the strength and modulus. The width of the specimen is made larger compared to that of typical unidirectional ceramic composites to avoid scattering of the data. Crosshead speed was set at 0.008 mm/sec. The relationships of applied load (P) versus displacement (δ) were recorded during the test. The ultimate load (P_{max}) were taken for the calculation of flexural strength (σ_{max}) and modulus (E) according to the following equations

$$\sigma_{max} = 3P_{max}L/2wh^2 \quad (2)$$

$$E = P_{max}L^3/4wh^3\delta \quad (3)$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Effect of Liquid Oxidation Reaction

In order to enhance the bonding between carbon fabrics and alumina matrix as well as interlayer shear strength, liquid oxidation reaction was adopted to modify the surface condition of carbon fabrics. Nitric acid was used in the liquid oxidation reaction. The existence of shallow grooves on the surface of one-hour treated fibers was observed. After 6 hour treatment, the grooves become deeper; furthermore the outside layer have been etched as some fragments and then peeled off until the surfaces becomes rougher and rugged. This phenomena is beneficial for interfacial bonding due to more contacts between matrix particles and fibers. By liquid oxidation reaction, some active oxide functional groups are attached to the surface of carbon fabrics, such as hydroxyl group, ester group, carboxylic acid group, and carbonyl group. These functional groups were verified by IR spectrum for the surface of treated fibers [11]. After 300 minute treatment, the distribution of those functional groups is as follows: 80% for hydroxyl, 6% for carbonyl, 6% for carboxylic acid, and 8% for ester, respectively. Those active oxide groups may react with matrix particles and silica gels leading to chemical bonding between fibers and matrix. Treated carbon fabrics with active functional groups on their surfaces can have high affinity with silica in the matrix. Some of those groups have negative charge, such as hydroxyl. They attract hydrogen atoms with positive charge in silanol group on the surface of silica. Hence, during hot pressing, those

active functional groups can react with silanol via dehydration process and result in siloxane, then chemical bonds were formed [12]. Furthermore, silica may react with alumina and produce mullite with lower melting point resulting in better interfacial bonding. The evidences can be supported from several figures that discussed below.

Figs. 2(a) and 2(b) show cross sections of hot pressed composites with treated and untreated carbon fabrics, respectively. After cutting and polishing, the former shows better infiltration of matrix in the intrayarn pores inferring better bonding between fibers and matrix. While the latter shows worse infiltration corresponding to poor bonding at the interface. Fracture surfaces perpendicular to treated carbon fibers of 2-D carbon/alumina composites are flat indicating complete bonding between fibers and matrix (Fig. 3(a)). However, it seems that incomplete bonding between fibers and matrix occurs for composites with untreated carbon fibers because the surface of composites is likely in a molten state as shown in Fig. 3(b). The incomplete bonding may be due to the reaction of sizing on the carbon fabrics with silica gels. By our observation, it is found that the distribution of alumina matrix is inhomogeneous and sintering effect is nonuniform in two kinds of pore, interyarn pores and intrayarn pores. This may lead to the reduction of strength of composites. The content of matrix materials in intrayarn pores is less because they are much smaller compared to interyarn pores so that infiltration is more difficult. Furthermore, during hot pressing, fibers around intrayarn pores constrains matrix shrinkage more than fibers around interyarn pores. Both reasons result in poor bonding between fibers around intrayarn pores and matrix particles, but better bonding between fibers around interyarn pores and matrix particles as shown in Figs. 3 (a) and (b).

The influence of liquid oxidation reaction on fracture toughness of 2-D carbon/alumina composites is shown in Table 1. Composites with untreated fibers have higher fracture toughness than those of composites with treated fibers. It is because that the former have poor bonding at fiber/matrix interface so that propagation of cracks may go through interface. Its porosity is somewhat higher than that of the latter as can be compared by the final densities from Table 1. The above reasons explain why composites with untreated fibers obtain better fracture toughness. But, in Table 2, it is shown that composites with untreated fibers obtain both lower flexural strength and modulus of elasticity as compared to those of composites with treated fibers due to better bonding between fibers and matrix.

Fig. 2: 2-D carbon/alumina composites with cross sections parallel to the hot pressing direction showing (a) better infiltration in the intrayarn pores among treated carbon fibers inferring better bonding between matrix and fibers in this region, (b) worse infiltration in the intrayarn pores among untreated carbon fibers

Fig. 3: Fracture surfaces of 2-D carbon/alumina composites perpendicular to the fibers showing (a) complete bonding between treated carbon fibers and matrix, (b) incomplete bonding between untreated carbon fibers and matrix

Table 1: Results of fracture toughness of 2-D carbon fabric/ Al_2O_3 ceramic matrix composites

Composite type	K_{IC} ($MPa \cdot m^{1/2}$)	Hv (GPa)	Green density (% TD)	Final density (% TD)
fiber untreated ($V_f = 33.7\%$)	7.0 ± 0.2	5.06	77.1	88.0
fiber treated ($V_f = 33.7\%$)	6.5 ± 0.1	4.6	71.2	89.9
fiber treated ($V_f = 21.5\%$)	2.0 ± 0.2	8.73	79.2	81.1

Table 2: Flexural strength and modulus of 2-D carbon fabric/ Al_2O_3 ceramic matrix composites

Composite type	Flexural strength (MPa)	Modulus of elasticity (MPa)
fiber untreated ($V_f = 33.7\%$)	30.4 ± 7.4	649.5 ± 238.1
fiber treated ($V_f = 33.7\%$)	51.7 ± 4.3	2081.4 ± 494.8
fiber treated ($V_f = 21.5\%$)	76.7 ± 31.3	608.5 ± 212

Effect of Fiber Volume Fraction

The fracture toughness of composites increase with the increase of fiber volume fraction as shown in Table 1. It is known that fibers in ceramics can inhibit the propagation of cracks resulting in the increase of fracture toughness. The influence of volume fraction of fibers V_f on both flexural strength and modulus of elasticity is shown in Table 2. For lower fiber

volume fraction, less constraint of matrix shrinkage during sintering from fiber fabrics results in better densification and less porosity of matrix particles. This leads to higher strength. However, the sparse fiber yarns in the fabrics can distort during their preparation or infiltration of the composite resulting in its lower modulus of elasticity.

The failure procedure of 2-D carbon/alumina composites with untreated carbon fibers can be described by Fig. 4. Arabic numerals represent the sequence of the procedure. Cracks initiate at the matrix between fabric layer (1) and propagate at the interface between fiber layer and matrix. When cracks meet fiber yarns perpendicular to the paper plane (weft yarns), they propagate through intrayarn pores (2). Later, cracks would meet the fiber yarns parallel to the paper plane (warp yarns) and continue to propagate at the interface between fiber yarns and matrix (3). Eventually, as the energy of cracks is large enough, it breaks the fiber yarns parallel to the paper plane (4) and composites fail. According to the observation, most of cracks in the composite with untreated carbon fibers locate at interlayer matrix, between weft and warp yarns, inside weft yarns, and on warp yarns. The distribution of cracks is uniform. On the other hand, cracks in the composite with treated carbon fibers are located at interlayer matrix and inside weft yarns near matrix-fiber interface. The distribution of cracks is nonuniform and dense around large pores. An overview of failure of 2-D carbon/alumina composites can be seen in Fig. 5. Some transverse microcracks can be found in the photographs. Interlayer delamination is the major failure mode of composites with treated fibers (Fig. 5(a)) because interlaminar shear strength of 2-D ceramic composites is intrinsically weak and cracks may propagate through matrix between layers instead of stronger interface between fibers and matrix. But local kinking is the major failure mode of composites with untreated fibers (Fig. 5(b)) because cracks could propagate at weaker interface under large compressive stresses and then local fibers would bend or kink without the constraint of matrix.

Fig. 4: Failure procedure of 2-D carbon/alumina composites with untreated carbon fibers; Arabic numerals representing the sequence of the procedure

Fig. 5(a): Overview of failure of 2-D carbon/alumina composites showing first major failure mode delamination (fibers treated)

Fig. 5(b): Overview of failure of 2-D carbon/alumina composites showing second major failure modes local kinking (fibers untreated)

CONCLUSIONS

2-D carbon/alumina composites were successfully fabricated by the pressure infiltration method. The fracture toughness increases but flexural strength decreases with increasing fiber volume fraction. Composites with untreated carbon fabrics have high fracture toughness of $7.0 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$, lower flexural strength of 30.4 MPa, and lower modulus of elasticity of 649.5 MPa. But composites with treated carbon fabrics by liquid oxidation reaction have lower fracture toughness of $6.5 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$, higher flexural strength of 51.7 MPa, and higher modulus of elasticity of 2081.4 MPa. Better bonding between treated fibers and matrix was found by scanning electron microscopic observation.

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